

SYNTHESIS OF POLYMER BASES BASED ON INULIN¹Abdullaev O.Kh.²Khusenov A.Sh.²Rakhmanberdiev G.

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Relevance: In recent decades, researchers have paid special attention to natural polymers as a basis for creating biocompatible materials that are widely used in medicine, pharmaceuticals, food and cosmetics industries. One of these promising polysaccharides is inulin, a plant heteropolysaccharide consisting mainly of fructose residues. Inulin has a number of valuable properties: it is non-toxic, resistant to human digestive enzymes and can be chemically modified, which makes it attractive for obtaining new functional materials. Due to its bioavailability and ability to structural modification, inulin opens up wide opportunities for creating materials with adjustable properties. For example, various polymer bases with specified physicochemical and biological properties can be created on the basis of inulin. In turn, polymer bases can find application as drug carriers, as well as as components of hydrogel systems and composite materials.

Purpose of the study: Synthesis of polymeric bases with different physicochemical properties by chemical modification of inulin.

Materials and methods: The polymer bases were synthesized by chemical modification of inulin. For this purpose, inulin was preliminarily modified with thionyl chloride in a dimethylformamide medium for 3 hours and to=70°C. Then, hydrazine was added to the aqueous solution of the synthesized chlorinulin at a molar ratio of inulin:hydrazine=1:1-5. The reaction proceeded at t°=50-70°C and a time of 0.5-10 hours. The obtained samples were purified by dialysis and isolated by freeze-drying. The synthesized samples were analyzed by FTIR spectroscopy, gel chromatography, titration, elemental analysis, and the pK_a value and the zeta potential value were calculated.

Results: In the FTIR spectrum of the inulin derivative containing hydrazine fragments, an intense absorption band was observed in the region of 2874 cm⁻¹ related to the vibration of -NH₂ groups. Absorption in the region of 1580 cm⁻¹ was related to the deformation vibrations of primary amino groups. The molecular weight of aminated inulin was 3500-5600 Da. Based on the nitrogen content, it was calculated that the degree of substitution of the synthesized samples was 27-50 mol%. Using the acidimetric titration method, it was found that the pK_a value of inulin derivatives was 7.4-8.0 and depended on the degree of substitution. In addition, the introduction of hydrazine molecules into the inulin structure gave the polysaccharide a positive charge and their zeta potential value was 5.4-18.7 mV. From this we can conclude that the introduction of hydrazine molecules into the structure of inulin provides the entire macrochain with the properties of polymeric bases.

Conclusions: By means of chemical addition of hydrazine to chlorinulin new derivatives with properties of polymer bases were synthesized. The structure, molecular weight and properties of the obtained derivatives of inulin were studied by methods of FTIR spectroscopy, gel chromatography, elemental analysis, acidimetric titration, etc. First of all, the developed method of inulin modification allows to control the properties of the polymer chain, opening up possibilities for further targeted application.